

ISic3630

I.Sicily inscription 3630

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

stone

Object

stone

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Selinunte, private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645702

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 59.1126

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 2010.0643

Rocca, G. 2009. Nuove iscrizioni da Selinunte. Alessandria. At 12-16 no.3

Rocca, G. 2009. Due inediti da Selinunte. In Antonetti, C., De Vido, S.(eds.), *Temì selinuntini*. Pisa. pp. 269-276. At 269-273 no.1 fig.1

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